

Managing challenging waste fractions: Mechanical recycling of light housings and environmental assessment

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Abstract

While the recycling landscape is currently dominated by the packaging sector - supported by robust legislation and mature logistics - expanding circularity to technical and medical waste streams is crucial for long-term industrial resilience. Achieving a sustainable plastics economy requires moving beyond simple "design for recycling." It necessitates an integrated approach involving "design for recyclates," where products are specifically engineered to incorporate high-quality secondary materials across multiple lifecycles. To bridge the current gap, underutilized technical input streams must be tapped, requiring both the technological evolution of mechanical recycling processes and a significant improvement in the quality of resulting secondary raw materials. A prime example of this challenge is found in Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE). The high diversity of polymers and the increasing prevalence of complex additives in electronic components, such as light housings, make high-grade recovery particularly difficult. This study addresses these complexities by evaluating various pre-treatment and recycling strategies aimed at optimizing the separation and mechanical processing of WEEE components. By focusing on silicone-contaminated polycarbonate (PC) fractions from light housings, the research seeks to establish pathways for reintroducing these materials into the polymer cycle at the highest possible quality level.

Keywords

WEEE plastics; mechanical recycling; light housings; PC recyclate; life cycle assessment (LCA)

1. Introduction

Currently, the majority of recycled plastics are derived from the packaging sector, which benefits from well-established legal frameworks and mature collection and logistics infrastructures (Plastics Europe 2024). In contrast, there is a significant lack of functional circular solutions for other waste streams, particularly those originating from technical and medical applications. To ensure a resilient, future-proof, and sustainable use of plastics, it is essential to expand the circular economy beyond the packaging industry. The recycling of waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE)-specifically examined in this study through the lens of light housings-poses a unique challenge. This is due to the extreme diversity of polymers and the increasing use of specialized additives.

This research evaluates various pre-treatment and recycling strategies to determine their efficiency in separating, processing, and potential reintroducing specific WEEE plastic components into the polymer cycle. The focus is placed on polycarbonate (PC) fractions contaminated with silicone. The goal is to achieve mechanical recycling of the highest possible quality, ensuring these technical plastics can be successfully reintegrated into high-value applications.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

The WEEE components, in this case the luminaire housings discussed, originate from actual waste collection by PRACT (PRACT ALPHA Solutions GmbH, Germany), the company that manufactures the luminaire housings. Due to the high material value of PC, the company ensures reverse logistics for WEEE waste as far as possible. These are post-consumer materials that were collected when old light housings, including light bulbs, which were replaced in larger facilities. The light bulbs were removed directly during collection. Therefore, only the light housings (tray, cover) with a foam-filled silicone seal are considered (see Fig.1).

Figure 1: Lighthouse housing 120cm x 10cm x 5cm

For density separation using the float sink process, salt (sodium chloride) was used to produce a solution with appropriate density of $\sim 1,16\text{g/cm}^3$ as a separation medium. Water was used for the cleaning and float sink process separation process. These resulting recyclates were evaluated against the recyclates from the same batch of PC luminaire housings, from which the silicone seal had been removed beforehand, as well as against the virgin PC used for the production of luminaire housings.

2.2. Methods

As part of this study, the raw material undergoes a multi-stage mechanical preparation and processing procedure consisting of comminution, separation (float sink separation), extrusion and subsequent injection moulding (Fig. 2). The aim is to separate the silicone seal from the PC in order to obtain a PC fraction. As part of the investigations, three grind sizes (4, 8, 12 mm) were produced and separated using two separation methods (wind sifting and float sink method). The practical approach is first outlined below and then described in detail in the corresponding subchapters. This publication presents the most important results used to evaluate the pre-treatment strategy. For the most promising process route, an ecological assessment in the form of a life cycle analysis (LCA) was also carried out in order to comprehensively quantify the environmental impact of the process and compare it with alternative treatment strategies.

Figure 2: Processes and nomenclature of the mechanical recycling approach

2.2.1. FTIR for Analysis of the granulate to evaluate foreign polymers in the recycle

The recycle produced is analysed using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) to identify other foreign polymers and determine the effectiveness of the separation quality. The polymer was measured using a FTIR microscope LUMOS II (Bruker Optik GmbH, Germany) in attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode. FTIR spectra were recorded using a scan time of 30 scans, in attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode, over a wavenumber range of 4000–750 cm^{-1} .

2.2.2. Pyrolyse GC/MS for Analysis of the granulate to evaluate foreign polymers in the recycle

The results show that the silicone material was successfully separated across all particle sizes. The results suggest minimal traces of silicone, but these are not clearly discernible in any of the results. The ISQ 7000 GC-MS system with double shot pyrolysator (ThermoFisher Scientific / Frontier Lab, USA) was used to determine the chemical composition of the recycled materials produced, i.e. to determine the silicone content.

2.2.3. Digital microscope

Randomly selected samples were evaluated also by imaging using a Leica DVM6 A 3D digital microscope (Leica Microsystems, Germany) to evaluate the silicone particles in the matrix.

2.3. Pre-Treatment Mechanical recycling

2.3.1. Shredding and separation

Shredding is an important step in the recycling process. The material supplied was shredded using a Wanner Dynamic 25.38S universal cutting mill (Wanner Technik GmbH, Germany) with a grid size of 4, 8 and 12 mm. The aim of the three particle sizes is to test the influence of particle size on the separation effectiveness of the materials during the density separation processes. The following processes are carried out for all particle sizes (Fig.3).

Figure 3: Shredded material with a particle size of 4, 8, 12 mm

Another key step in pre-treatment is density separation. This is carried out in two ways as part of the project (see tab.1).

Considering the density of PC (1.2 g/cm³) and silicone foam 0.15 and 0.8 g/cm³ [3], the float-sink separation (FS) with a solution at ~1,16g/cm³: The particles are suspended in water: materials with lower density float, denser particles sink, enabling separable fractionation according to density. Preliminary tests on effectiveness were carried out, followed by semi-industrial trials using a Circulyer hydrocyclone centrifugal separator (Circulyzer GmbH, Austria). This is a wet mechanical processing plant that efficiently washes and separates mixed plastic and waste fractions. Using float sink/centrifugal force technology, the plastics are recovered for recycling.

Wind sifting (WS) using a WANNER 25.38S cyclone separator (Wanner Technik GmbH, Germany): the particles are separated by an air stream; light materials are carried away by the stream, while heavy particles remain behind, thus also achieving density-based separation. Experiments were also carried out involving the sequential application of both methods with a particle size of 8mm.

In preparation for this step, density measurements were carried out on the individual components in accordance with ISO 1183-1 to ensure a pure separation fraction. After extrusion of the differently pre-treated samples, a density determination was also carried out on the test specimens.

Table 1: Nomenclature of the fractions. FS: Float Sink, WS: Wind sifting

Particle size	4 mm		8mm		12mm		8mm	8mm	8mm
Separation	FS	WS	FS	WS	FS	WS	WS+FS	seal dismantled	virgin
Sample	FS4	WS4	FS8	WS8	FS12	WS12	WFS8	PC-D	PC-V

2.4. Characterisation and Mechanical testing

The melt volume rate (MVR) of the regranulates was determined two times according to DIN EN ISO 1133 using an extrusion plastometer MFR/MVR ZwickRoell Aflow (ZwickRoell GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) at 280 °C under 2.16 kg.

Test specimens for mechanical testing according to the DIN EN ISO 527-1 (type CW, according to ISO 3167, ISO 294) were produced from the regranulate in an injection moulding machine BOY XS (Dr. Boy GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). Processing was carried out under the usual process parameters for PC (285 °C). The produced test specimens were then conditioned in accordance with ISO 291 at 23°C for 48 hours. Mechanical characterisation includes tensile testing based on DIN EN ISO 527-2 at room temperature using a ZwickRoell Z030 TEW material testing machine (ZwickRoell GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). Eight samples are tested for each parameter to determine the mean value. Bending tests were performed five times according to DIN EN ISO 178 using the same material testing machine used for the tensile testing. The impact strength test was determined in accordance with ISO 179-2 using a ZwickRoell HIT25P pendulum impact tester (ZwickRoell GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). Ten test specimens with type 1 according to ISO 179-1 were tested for each material.

2.5. Environmental assessment

The environmental impacts were assessed by performing a LCA of the most promising recycling approach and the current waste treatment, incineration with energy recovery. The system boundaries were defined using a 'cut-off' approach from the collected waste to the production of regranulate for injection moulding. For reference, the results of the recycling approach were compared to the impacts of virgin material production and the current waste treatment, incineration with energy recovery. The virgin material to be replaced was modelled PC. As much data as possible was taken from lab-scale and semi-industrial scale plants and was complemented by literature data [1]. Thereby, the process data for the developed mechanical recycling approach was obtained for all processes listed in Table 2. The life cycle inventories for the environmental assessment were prepared using the 'LCA For Experts' software (formerly known as 'GaBi', version 10.9.1.17) and the Managed LCA Database (formerly known as 'GaBi database', version 2025.1). More information on the life cycle inventories and underlying assumptions is provided in the Supplementary Information.

The environmental impacts were calculated using the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 method provided by the European Commission. The results of the 16 assessed environmental impact categories that are covered by the EF 3.1 method were summarized using a normalized and weighted single score with normalisation and weighting factors [2]. For further examination of the influence of the individual data points, a scenario analysis was carried out. In this

analysis, the efficiency of float sink separation was reduced from the industrial base scenario to a laboratory scale (scenario 1) and further increased to a standardized industrial-scale process (scenario 2). Further information on the underlying assumptions is provided in the Supplementary Information.

Table2: Processes modelled for the mechanical recycling approach; scale indication based on equipment throughput (semi-industrial = low end of industrial throughput)

Process	Equipment name	Data source	Scale
Shredding (8 mm)	25.38s cutting mill (Wanner Technik GmbH, Germany)	Collected data	Lab
Float sink-separation	‘Circulyzer’ separation unit for density separation	Estimated data	Industrial
Washing	–	Literature data	Industrial
Drying	–	Literature data	Industrial
Extrusion	Process 16 laboratory extruder (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germany)	Estimated data	Lab
Granulation	–	Dataset	Industrial

3. Results and Discussion

Separation

The following section describes the different grinding sizes in the separation processes. It includes a visual inspection of the light and heavy fractions in the windsifting process and of the floating and sinking fractions in the float sink separation process.

In preparation, the PC housings and silicone were examined for density. The results according to ISO 1183-1 show a density of 1.2 g/cm³ for PC. The silicone seal could not be measured because it has a lower density than the isopropanol used in the test (0.78–0.79 g/cm³). According to the literature [3], the density of silicone foam or sponge is between 0.15 and 0.8 g/cm³, which fits within the range here.

Windsifting

All three grind sizes were fed into the wind sifter. The 4 mm grind size shows a clear separation of the light fraction or silicone (Fig. 4) but due to the small particle size, PC particles were also detected as “dust” or material with a low density. The heavy fraction was examined randomly under a digital microscope. A silicone-free PC fraction was identified here.

With the 8 mm grind size (Fig.5), a separation is visible; small particles, impurities, and dust are separated with the light fraction. The heavy fraction shows isolated larger particles of silicone. The separation is inhibited by the seal “sticking” to the PC. Images The 12 mm grind size still shows larger pieces of the silicone seal (Fig.6) in the heavy fraction and therefore does not show effective separation.

Figure 4: Windsifting 4 mm

Figure 5: Windsifting 8 mm

Figure 6: Windsifting 12 mm

The result of the windsifting shows that just one of the tested particle size gives acceptable results regarding separation by means of wind sifting. Separation by particle size 4 mm shows a minimized proportion of silicon impurities.

Float Sink Separation

The float sink separation at a grind size of 4 mm causes material to accumulate below the water in the float fraction, inhibiting separation and preventing light particles from separating. The floating fraction accumulates as a result of physical effects. Particle interactions and hindered settling occur, preventing separation. Furthermore, interfacial tension and air bubbles can lead to a capillary effect (Fig.7).

Figure 7 Float Sink Separation 4 mm

This effect does not occur at a grind size of 8 mm (Fig.8). With a particle size of 8 mm, there is a reduced influence of interfacial forces, less impeded sedimentation, fewer particle interactions, and higher settling and rising rates, so that the particles can be clearly separated into settling and flotation fractions according to their density. A clear separation can be seen with a particle size of 8 mm. The separation shows that PC particles can be found in the floating fraction in addition to silicone, but there are almost no silicone fragments in the sinking fraction (Fig.8).

Figure 8: Float Sink Separation 8 mm

A clear separation was also observed with a screen size of 12 mm (Fig. 9), similar to the description above. After a visual inspection, many large silicone flakes can be seen in the floating fraction.

Figure 9: Float Sink Separation 12 mm

Result of the separation options

Once both separation processes had been completed, the results were examined visually in order to eliminate the insufficiently separable components. The separation quality in the wind sifting process deteriorates as particle size increases. Only the separation at 4 mm allows visual identification of the separation of the silicone from the PC. In the further course of the experiments, only the heavy fraction of the 4 mm particle size will be considered from the wind sifting.

When examining the separation using float sink separation, it is evident that separation at 4 mm is hampered by physical effects. Clumping of the material prevents satisfactory separation of the silicone from the PC. The sink fraction of the 8 mm particle size shows, upon visual inspection, a virtually silicone-free PC fraction, which is why it is still being considered. A material with downstream wind sifting and float sink separation is also being tested. The following section presents a comparison of the properties of the various separated fractions with a PC fraction from which silicone has been previously removed by hand. A comparison with virgin material is also provided. The results are intended to demonstrate the most effective separation of the silicone content.

3.1. Mechanical testing and characterization of the recycled material

The following section shows the results (Fig.13) of the sinking fraction from 8 mm float sink separation (FS8), the heavy fraction from 4 mm wind sifting (WS4), and the sequentially connected 8 mm fraction from SST and WS (WFS8). This is followed by a comparison with the same fraction from PC light housings (PC-D), in which the silicone seal was removed, and the new material from the light housings (PC-V). For the mechanical tests, granulates and test specimens were produced as shown in Figure 10

Figure 10: Granules and test specimen from windsifting, float sink separation and from a combination of both methods

3.1.1. Thermal Behavior and Rheological Properties

The practically determined density of the separated material fractions increases in the following order: **PC-V** (1.20 g/cm^3) < **PC-D** (1.22 g/cm^3) < **FS8** (1.23 g/cm^3) \approx **WFS8** (1.23 g/cm^3) < **WS4** (1.24 g/cm^3). PC-V shows the lowest density at approximately 1.20 g/cm^3 . In contrast, all fractions that previously contained silicone seals exhibit slightly higher densities (approximately $1.23\text{--}1.24 \text{ g/cm}^3$).

At first glance, this increase could be attributed to residual silicone contamination. However, pure silicone materials such as polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) typically exhibit densities in the range of $1.05\text{--}1.15 \text{ g/cm}^3$ [4], which are lower than the density of polycarbonate. Therefore, the observed density increase of approximately 3.3 % compared to PC-V cannot be explained solely by the intrinsic density of silicone residues.

A more likely explanation is that the silicone-containing fractions also contain additional contaminants, additives, or heterogeneous material components introduced during use or separation. Furthermore, the presence of incompatible phases such as PC and silicone residues may alter the morphology of the material and influence the experimentally determined bulk density [5].

The MFR is significantly higher for all recyclates compared to PC-V ($\approx 7 \text{ g/10 min}$). Even PC-D ($\sim 13 \text{ g/10 min}$) shows an increased MFR. The highest values occur in WFS8 ($\sim 25 \text{ g/10 min}$) and FS8 ($\sim 22 \text{ g/10 min}$), while WS4 ($\sim 15 \text{ g/10 min}$) is closer to PC-D. Similarly, all recyclates show an increased MFR compared to PC-V. Often, a higher MFR means a lower average molar mass, as shorter polymer chains flow more easily. Since the MFR in linear thermoplastics correlates inversely with the molar mass, these results indicate additional thermomechanical degradation during processing and also the use phase.

The DSC curves of the samples (see Figure 11) show, amongst other things, a typical PC curve for PC-D (grey), which contains no silicone contaminants. The T_g is typically around $146 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and there are no signs of cross-linking (as the material melts and exhibits a clear glass transition).

All fractions show a clear glass transition at approx. 143 - 146 °C. The differences between the samples are small but measurable and suggest variation-induced morphological changes, e.g. slight material variations, possibly differing additive/filler contents, or slight differences in chain length due to recycling processes. In this case, the differences are likely due to the silicone content. An additional thermal effect is observable at approx. 127 °C, which indicates structural relaxation or reorganisation processes.

Figure 11: DSC curves of the fractions

PC undergoes chain shortening due to hydrolytic and thermal cleavage of the carbonate groups at elevated temperatures and in the presence of residual moisture [6–8]. Similarly, mechanical recycling and aging of polycarbonate show that chain breaks occur, primarily due to hydrolytic and thermo-oxidative degradation processes.. This results in a reduction in molecular weight, which in turn increases the melt flow rate (MFR) due to decreased melt viscosity. PC-V has a lower MFR due to having not been in use and therefore shows no signs of ageing. PC-D, the silicone-free fraction, has a slightly increased MFR, indicating chain breakage due to the period of use. The silicone-contaminated fractions also show signs of ageing, as does PC-D, but here the MFR increases significantly, which is attributable to the contamination. The combined pre-treatment (WFS8) thus leads to the greatest reduction in molecular weight [9, 10].

In the further course of the study, it could be inferred that mechanical performance might be influenced to a greater extent by morphological and interphase effects than by moderate differences in molecular weight.

3.1.2. Tensile modulus and tensile strength

All recycled materials exhibit higher tensile moduli ($\approx 2620 - 2820$ MPa) than PC-V (~ 2430 MPa). According to classical composite theory [11], the elastic modulus of a polymer multiphase system can increase if rigid filler particles are present, if interfaces restrict matrix mobility, or if morphological constraints limit relaxation processes. WS4 exhibits the lowest modulus among the recycled materials (~ 2620 MPa), which suggests an unfavourable phase distribution or increased structural inhomogeneity. This can be inferred from the microscopic images (Fig. 12), which show a brittle surface. This increase is characteristic of multiphase systems with rigid inclusions or restricted chain mobility. WFS8 is very close to the value of PC-D (~ 2770 MPa) and thus indicates comparable structural integrity. Minimal contamination has less of an effect on the modulus of elasticity than, for example, on impact strength, so all samples are comparable. The tensile strength is ranked as follows **FS8** \approx **WFS8** $>$ **PC-D** $>$ **PC-V** $>$ **WS4**. At ~ 60 MPa, WS4 shows a significant reduction compared to the other systems, while FS8 and WFS8, at ~ 70 MPa, are even higher than PC-D ($\sim 66-67$ MPa). In incompatible polymer blends, a poorly adhering dispersed phase typically leads to excessive stress and premature cavitation [12]. Silicone elastomers have very low surface energy and, without compatibilization, exhibit only low interfacial adhesion to polycarbonate. Under tensile stress, segregation,

particle detachment, and microcracking can therefore occur. As noted in the section above, the significant reduction in strength in WS4 therefore points to the presence of remaining finely dispersed silicone particles, a weak interfacial bond and an increased defect density acting as crack initiation sites (see Fig. 12).

Figure 12: Microscopic images of silicone particles in PC fractions

The high values of FS8 and, in particular, WFS8, on the other hand, demonstrate an effective reduction in critical silicone content and thus improved stress transfer within the PC matrix [13]. Although silicone particles can also be seen here, they exhibit fewer microcracks in the matrix (see Fig. xx) and thus provide better interfacial adhesion between PC and silicone

3.1.3. Impact strength

Impact strength is particularly sensitive to morphological defects and interfacial adhesion. The measured values show **PC-D ≈ WFS8 ≈ FS8 >> WS4 ≈ PC-V**. WS4 shows a significant reduction at $\sim 80 \text{ kJ/m}^2$, while FS8 and WFS8 ($\sim 115 \text{ kJ/m}^2$) almost reach the level of PC-D ($\sim 118 \text{ kJ/m}^2$). The failure behavior of polycarbonate is characterized by shear deformation and plastic energy dissipation. Weakly bound inclusions act as crack initiators and promote brittle failure [14, 15]. The low impact strength of WS4 might therefore suggest a potentially increased occurrence of interfacial defects. Although finer grinding (4 mm) can promote the exposure of the silicone seal, it does not appear to lead to its sufficient separation. Instead, finely distributed, poorly adhering silicone residues may form, which significantly reduce toughness. The combined strategy (WFS8), on the other hand, enables almost complete restoration of toughness to PC-D levels.

Figure 13: Mechanical test results from the fractions

3.1.4. Overall assessment of pre-treatment strategies

From a materials science perspective, three competing mechanisms determine mechanical performance

- Residual content and morphology of the silicone phase,
- Interfacial adhesion between PC and silicone,
- Molecular weight reduction due to thermomechanical stress.

Although WFS8 has the highest MFR (and thus the strongest molecular weight reduction), this material achieves the best mechanical properties among the silicone-containing recyclates. This illustrates that, in the range investigated, the elimination of interphase defects has a greater influence on mechanical integrity than moderate chain shortening. Wind separation alone (WS4) is clearly inferior in mechanical terms, as silicone separation is insufficient and the resulting defect density significantly reduces load-bearing capacity and toughness.

Float sink separation (FS8) is already an effective measure for reducing silicone-containing impurities.

The sequential combination of both processes (WFS8) proves to be the most effective pre-treatment strategy. It delivers

- mechanical properties close to PC-D,
- high tensile strength,
- high impact strength,
- homogeneous mechanical behavior

3.2. Environmental assessment

For the environmental assessment, the mechanical recycling approach is compared to the current waste treatment, incineration with energy recovery (see Fig. x). All results for the individual impact categories without normalization and weighting are provided in the Supplementary Information.

Figure 14 Environmental impacts (EF 3.1 Single score) for mechanical recycling and incineration with energy recovery of 1 kg of lamp cases (100%: mechanical recycling impacts) *material credit only applicable with appropriate product application

Incineration has higher impacts, namely 448% of the recycling impacts, but receives credits (-372%) for recovering electricity and heat. In general, it is expected that the credits for energy recovery are going to decrease in the future, when more sustainable energy production processes are substituted. However, currently, incineration has net impacts of 76% of the recycling impacts after totalling the impacts and credits.

On the other hand, the recycling of 1 kg of lamp cases produces 788 g of regranulate. An environmental credit can be achieved when the recyclate can substitute the same amount of virgin material in a product application similar to the energy credits. In that case, the material credit for avoiding virgin PC production (-1481%) leads to net-negative environmental impacts for the mechanical recycling approach (-1381%) that are much lower than the net impacts of the incineration process. The scenario analysis covers two scenarios with decreased and increased energy efficiency of the float sink separation, the results are provided in Figure x. Two float sink separation processes are included in the mechanical recycling approach and changes in their energy demand also affect the overall environmental impacts. In the assessed scenarios, the Single score results vary from 274% of the base scenario result for a lower energy efficiency and 98% for the higher energy efficiency. On one hand, this highlights the importance of a precise data collection process. On the other hand, it illustrates that even while the impacts of the recycling process may vary depending on process configurations, substituting virgin material may still lead to overall net-negative environmental impacts for the recycling approach.

Figure 15 Environmental impacts (EF 3.1 Single score) for two assessed scenarios regarding the float sink separation (100%: base scenario impacts)

4. Conclusions

As part of this study, various pre-treatment strategies (grinding size and dry and wet separation methods) for recycling PC light housings with integrated silicone seals were investigated. The results showed that the mechanical properties of silicone-contaminated PC recyclates are largely determined by the efficiency of silicone separation and the resulting morphology. Furthermore, it was determined that windsifting alone is not sufficient as a pre-treatment and leads to a significant reduction in tensile strength and impact strength due to increased interphase defects. At the same time, float sink separation can considerably improve mechanical performance. The combination of both processes represents the best pre-treatment strategy, as it raises the mechanical properties to almost the level of silicone-free recyclates.

One limitation of this study is that the evaluation of recycled material performance is restricted to a pre-sorted real waste. In practice, recycling streams are mostly mixed and exhibit greater variations in silicone content, particle size distribution, and type of contaminants, which could affect the efficiency of pre-treatment strategies and the resulting mechanical properties. Regarding the environmental impacts, in this study, the mechanical properties of the recycled material were only compared to other recyclates. Therefore, without a product application, no statements on the substitution potential for virgin PC and therefore the actual environmental benefits are possible. However, since the PC recyclates are commercially available, there is a certain material demand on the market. Also, the LCA results were calculated from a mix of the available lab-scale and semi-industrial scale data and literature data. The scenario analysis illustrates how this influences the potential environmental impacts. The model used for the calculations represents the status quo of the recycling approach. Future implementation on a larger scale may result in different results due to an increased efficiency or different configurations of the modelled processes.

Future work should include pilot tests, more comprehensive material characterization, and aging studies to confirm the scalability and long-term performance of the proposed treatment methods. The life cycle assessment shows that the developed recycling approach can lead to a reduction of the environmental impacts when the recycled material substitutes virgin material. However, the net savings depend on the actual substitution. The scenario analysis also illustrates the need for representative data, which depends on the actual implementation of the recycling approach within current waste management systems.

Supplementary Information

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A. Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)

The life cycle inventories are listed in Table 4.1 to Table 4.6. The following general assumptions were applied:

- Electricity is supplied by the general German electricity mix (2022). Process water supply is modelled as tap water from groundwater.
- Residual waste is treated as commercial waste. For plastic residues, the process 'DE: Plastics (unspecified) in waste incineration plant (14.4% H₂O content)' was applied including credits for energy recovery. For all other residues, the process 'DE: Commercial waste in municipal waste incineration plant (0% H₂O content)' was applied including credits for energy recovery.
- For the float sink-separation, it was assumed that around 5.5 kg of water are required per 1 kg of treated waste according to process estimations that align with literature values [1]. Since most of the water is reused, it was assumed that only 3 % of the required water is supplied from freshwater to account for the less frequent total water exchanges.
- As the processes of washing and drying were carried out manually, no energy consumption data was recorded. Therefore, to account for this thermal and electrical energy consumption on industrial scale, data from Larrain et al. [1] was used.
- No primary data was available for granulation of the extrudate. Therefore, a generic dataset was used to account for these processes.
- Transport processes were not considered, as it was assumed that all recycling processes would be combined at the same location.
- For reference, the environmental impacts were compared to virgin material and an alternative disposal route. Virgin PC material was modelled using the 'DE: Polycarbonate granulate (PC)' process.
- For the alternative disposal route, it was assumed that the waste stream would usually be incinerated in Germany with energy recovery. This was modelled using the same processes as the ones used for the residual waste including credits for energy recovery.

Table 4.1: Life cycle inventory for the shredding (8 mm)

Shredding (8 mm)				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Waste stream (lamp housings)	5.14	kg	No burdens (cut-off)	–
Electricity	5.3	MJ		DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Lamp housings (shredded)	4.88	kg	–	–
Residual waste	0.26	kg	Commercial waste	DE: Commercial waste in municipal waste incineration plant (0% H ₂ O content)

Table 4.2: Life cycle inventory for the float sink-separation

Float sink-separation				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Lamp housings (shredded)	1.00	kg	–	–
Electricity	0.015	kWh	Data tested in a sensitivity analysis	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Water	1.31	kg	Assumption (3 % of required amount)	DE: Tap water from groundwater
Salt	0.35	kg	–	DE: Sodium chloride (rock salt)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Sinking fraction (for further use)	0.93	kg	–	–
Floating fraction (waste)	0.04	kg	Commercial waste (silicone)	DE: Plastics (unspecified) in waste incineration plant (14.4% H ₂ O content)
Wastewater	1.66	kg	Assumption (3 % of required amount)	DE: Municipal wastewater treatment (mix)

Table 4.3: Life cycle inventory for washing

Washing				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Floating fraction	6.00	kg	–	–
Water	0.99	kg	Same assumption as for the float sink-separation (3 % of required amount)	DE: Tap water from groundwater
Electricity	0.173	kWh	Literature data [1]	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Washed floating fraction	6.00	kg	–	–
Wastewater	0.99	kg	Same assumption as for the float sink-separation (3 % of required amount)	DE: Municipal wastewater treatment (mix)

Table 4.4: Life cycle inventory for the drying

Drying				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Sinking fraction (for further use)	1.00	t	–	–
Electricity	18.2	kWh	Literature data [1]	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Thermal Energy	25.8	kWh	Literature data [1]	DE: Thermal energy mix (2021)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Dried sinking fraction	1.00	t	–	–

Table 4.5: Life cycle inventory for the extrusion

Extrusion				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Dried sinking fraction	3.00	kg	–	–
Electricity	1.26	MJ	Estimate based on previous runs with similar materials	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Extrudate	2.82	kg	–	–
Material losses	0.18	kg	Assumption: 6 % losses	DE: Plastics (unspecified) in waste incineration plant (14.4% H ₂ O content)

Table 4.6: Life cycle inventory for the granulation

Granulation				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Extrudate	1.00	kg	–	–
Granulation	1.00	kg	No primary data	DE: Granulator (30-1500 kg/h throughput)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Granulate (recycled)	1.00	kg	–	–

B. Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

The results of the life cycle impact assessment are listed in Table 4.7. The normalized and weighted Single Score results are presented alongside the individual impact category results. The results are scaled to the results of the developed recycling approach (100%) for data confidentiality reasons.

Table 4.7: Results of the life cycle impact assessment for the respective reference flow; for data confidentiality reasons, all results are scaled to the results of the developed recycling approach (100%)

Impact category	Unit	Recycling approach	Material credit for substitution of virgin PC (negative)	Incineration	Energy credit for substitution energy production (negative)
Reference flow		1 kg of waste	mass of produced recycle	1 kg of waste	amount of produced energy
Acidification	mol H+ eq	100%	-931%	88%	-302%
Climate Change	kg CO2 eq	100%	-882%	671%	-312%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	100%	-11197%	48%	-329%
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	100%	-441%	6%	-88%
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	100%	-777%	53%	-271%
Eutrophication, terr.	mol N eq	100%	-763%	97%	-266%
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	100%	-1196%	61%	-281%
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	100%	-658%	102%	-181%
Ionising radiation	kBq U235	100%	-503%	18%	-274%
Land Use	pt	100%	-546%	28%	-578%
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	100%	-481%	18%	-274%
Particulate matter	disease incidences	100%	-741%	90%	-209%
Photochem. ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	100%	-1202%	63%	-292%
Resource use, fossils	MJ	100%	-3741%	67%	-827%
Resource use, mineral and metals	kg Sb eq	100%	-782%	22%	-304%
Water use	m ³ world eq	100%	-184%	709%	-42%
Single Score	–	100%	-1481%	448%	-372%

The normalised results (in %) for material and energy credit are positive in some impact categories, which may seem counterintuitive at first glance. This is because the developed recycling approach generates waste that is incinerated. The energy produced during this incineration is credited when modelling the recycling approach. In some impact categories, this credit is higher than the impacts for energy and water consumed by the recycling approach. As a result, the numerical results for the recycling approach, which are used as a reference (as '100%'), are negative in some impact categories. Since the numerical results for material and energy credit are also negative (i.e. the same negative sign as for the recycling approach), the normalised results (in %) become positive in these impact categories, even though a credit is represented.

C. Scenario analysis

To assess the influence of individual data points, a scenario analysis was carried out for the electricity consumption of the float sink-separation. Different data was available and is listed in Table 4.8, the results are listed in Table 4.9.

Table 4.8: Data used for the scenario analysis on the electricity consumption of the float sink-separation

Scenario	Scale	Description	Electricity consumption (kWh/kg input)	Data used for sensitivity analysis (kWh/kg input)
Scenario 1 (low efficiency)	Lab	Results from own lab-scale test with an energy consumption of 0.4-0.6 kWh per test and throughput of 0.5-0.6 kg material per test	0.67-1.20	1.2
Base scenario	Industrial	Information on industrial scale of the same separation unit by the manufacturer with an energy consumption of 3-15 kWh/t [16]	0.003-0.015	0.015
Scenario 2 (high efficiency)	Industrial (standardized process)	Literature data [1]	0.0035	0.0035

Table 4.9: Results (EF 3.1 method) of the scenario analysis for the recycling of 1 kg of waste, all results are scaled to the results of the base scenario (100%)

Impact category	Unit	Scenario 1 (low efficiency)	Base scenario	Scenario 2 (high efficiency)
Acidification	mol H+ eq	278%	100%	98%
Climate Change	kg CO2 eq	238%	100%	99%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	284%	100%	98%
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	170%	100%	99%
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	248%	100%	99%
Eutrophication, terr.	mol N eq	245%	100%	99%
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	318%	100%	98%
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	227%	100%	99%
Ionising radiation	kBq U235	386%	100%	97%
Land Use	pt	409%	100%	97%
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	386%	100%	97%
Particulate matter	disease incidences	225%	100%	99%
Photochem. ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	244%	100%	99%
Resource use, fossils	MJ	460%	100%	97%
Resource use, mineral and metals	kg Sb eq	371%	100%	97%
Water use	m3 world eq	139%	100%	100%
Single Score	–	274%	100%	98%

Author contributions

Yasemin Celik: Project administration, Conceptualization, Writing–original draft, Investigation. Meret Jürgens: Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing–original draft, Niklas Rode: Project administration, Investigation. Madina Shamsuyeva: Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. Hans-Josef Endres: Supervision

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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Data availability

The data supporting this article have been included as part of the Supplementary Information.

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